

Clinical Reasoning: Flaccid Paraparesis Due to Paraneoplastic Syndrome and Depression Due to Frontal Lobe Metastasis from Adenocarcinoma Lung in a Patient with Pulmonary Tuberculosis and Benign Spindle Cell Tumor of Stomach

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ABSTRACT

Middle age man had flaccid paraparesis and depression. Chest radiograph was compatible with old pulmonary tuberculosis. Non-contrast CT scan head was normal. Benign spindle cell tumor was found in gastroscopy done for hematemesis and melaena. Autopsy revealed adenocarcinoma right lung and metastasis at right frontal lobe. Clinical reasoning and challenges in resource poor setting were discussed.

KEYWORDS: flaccid paraparesis, depression, pulmonary tuberculosis, adenocarcinoma lung, frontal lobe metastasis, benign spindle cell tumor of stomach

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INTRODUCTION

Flaccid paraparesis may result from infection, vitamin deficiency, peripheral neuropathy and carcinomatous neuropathy (metastatic and paraneoplastic syndrome) (Restrepo-Jiménez et al., 2018) (Theroux & Brenton, 2019) (Badawy et al., 2023) (Bahadoram et al., 2022) (Penfold et al., 2024) (Kim et al., 2015).

Depression may be functional or organic in etiology. Depressive symptoms may be secondary to the following

causes: (1) neurological causes such as cerebrovascular accident, multiple sclerosis, subdural hematoma, epilepsy, Parkinson disease, Alzheimer disease; (2) endocrinopathies such as diabetes mellitus, thyroid disorders, adrenal disorders; (3) metabolic disturbances such as hypercalcemia, hyponatremia; (4) medications/substances abuse like steroids, antihypertensives, anticonvulsants, antibiotics, sedatives, hypnotics, alcohol, stimulant withdrawal; (5) nutritional deficiencies such as vitamin B1, B2, B6, B12, D

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deficiency, iron or folate deficiency; (6) infectious diseases such as HIV and syphilis; and (7) malignancies (Cui et al., 2024) (H. Wang et al., 2021) (Thapar et al., 2022) (Hu et al., 2021) (Zakaria et al., 2022).

Lung cancer is the most common cancer in the world, and a leading cause of death in both men and women (Smolarz et al., 2025). It has relatively poor prognosis compared to other types of cancers. In early stages of lung cancer there are usually no signs or symptoms. Common clinical presentation is mainly respiratory symptoms; and early diagnosis and appropriate treatment determines survival (Buccheri & Ferrigno, n.d.). However, atypical presentations like knee pain, abdominal pain, visual symptoms were reported in some case series (Buccheri & Ferrigno, n.d.). Therefore, early detection and timely curative treatment remains a challenge.

Another problem is interplay between lung cancer and pulmonary TB particularly in developing countries where there is high prevalence of tuberculosis. Studies found that previous tuberculous infection (TB) and lung cancer had a significant relationship (Nair et al., 2017). Moreover, lung cancer can be misdiagnosed as pulmonary TB as the clinical symptoms and radiological findings of pulmonary TB, lung cancer, and non-TB mycobacteria lung infections are similar (Keikha & Esfahani, 2018) (Luo et al., 2024). In addition, Mahishi et al reported that histologically proved lung cancer was found in patients with confirmed TB (Mahishi et al., 2024). Therefore, clinical reasoning for step wise diagnosis may not be easy (Furlan et al., 2016).

Lung cancer originates from chronic inflammation and infection. Various investigations have pointed out that tuberculosis is an important risk factor for lung cancer occurrence. They reported that Mycobacterium tuberculosis (M.tb) in patients with TB induced tumor formation. Furthermore, some additional factors such as age, sex and smoking, accelerate the development of lung cancer after Mycobacterium tuberculosis infection (Qin et al., 2022) (Moon et al., 2023) (Sodeifian et al., 2024). According to systematic review and metaanalysis, history of pulmonary TB was an independent risk factor for lung cancer, especially in younger patients (Hwang et al., 2022). They also highlighted the awareness of this association among clinicians (Luo et al., 2024).

This case report described flaccid paraparesis and depression in patient with old case pulmonary tuberculosis. They were related with autopsy findings missed clinically.

CASE PRESENTATION

59 years old man presented with weak legs for one month. He had history of ischemic heart disease; and, stent was inserted to proximal left anterior descending artery one year ago. He was on 2 anti-platelets, atorvastatin and carvedilol. He also had history of pulmonary tuberculosis. He was treated with isoniazid, rifampicin, pyrazinamide and ethambutol for 6

months; and, completed 10 years ago. He was admitted to neurological ward for weakness of both lower limbs, weight loss and loss of appetite for one month. On neurological examination, higher cortical functions were intact; cranial nerves examination was normal; sensory system was intact; cerebellar signs were not detected; motor power was 3/5 in both lower limbs. Therefore, he was treated as chronic flaccid paraparesis without sensory involvement probably due to anti-tubercular drug induced peripheral neuropathy. Nerve conduction study revealed symmetrical length-dependent sensory-motor axonal polyneuropathy. He was given vitamins and physiotherapy.

CXR showed old infective changes at both upper zones and left middle zone. It is shown in photo (1 & 2). Psychiatrist treated with regular exercise in ward and found that tenderness on sacro-iliac joint. Thoraco-lumber spine X-rays were suggestive of thoraco-lumber spondylosis. Pelvic X-ray was normal. They are shown in photo (3 & 4).

The patient seemed to have depression as he had stress, weak legs and financial problem; early morning wakening; history of alcohol use; loss of pleasure; reduced rapport; tearful eye; and social problems. Moreover, he had some behavioral changes and depressive mood. Therefore, non-contrast CT scan head was done; it was normal. CT head photos are revealed in photo (5-13). Thus, he was treated as a case of 'major depressive disorder' with sertraline and alprazolam. During hospital stay, the patient passed melena stool. And, hemoglobin dropped to 8 gm%. Parenteral proton pump inhibitor, fluids and electrolyte replacement and blood transfusion were given. Gastroscopy detected possible bleeding source as erosive pangastritis, atrophic gastritis and subepithelial lesion at upper part of body of stomach (smooth, rounded, non-mobile and firm mass measuring 20 mm covered by inflamed-mucosa). Photo (14-20) reveal gastroscopy findings. Biopsy revealed chronic active erosive gastritis (negative for dysplasia) and benign spindle cell tumor, subepithelial lesion. Ultrasound abdomen showed gall stone without feature of cholecystitis and right pleural effusion.

After blood transfusion, hemoglobin rose to 11.5 gm%; total WBC count was $9.5 \times 10^9/L$; platelet count was $382 \times 10^9/L$. Few days later, he passed black tarry stool for 2 times. He became confused and deteriorated; febrile 102 °F; blood pressure dropped 80/60 mmHg; tachycardiac 112/minutes; crackles over both lungs more on right side. Although we did active treatment with fluids and electrolytes, proton pump, antibiotics and oxygen therapy, hypovolemic/septic shock was not revived. And, the patient passed away.

In autopsy, serious pleural effusion about 1,200 cc in right side; and left thoracic cavity had serious pleural effusion (100 cc) and pleural adhesion. They are shown in photo 21 and 22. There was a mass in right lung close to hilum and left lung had some areas of consolidation. They are demonstrated in

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photo (23 and 24). Histology was consistent with adenocarcinoma right lung. Photo (32) illustrates it.

Liver had mild congestion (photo 30) and spleen was soft and septic (photo 29). Kidneys were normal (photo 31). Heart was normal and coronary arteries were patent . They are shown in photo (27).

Stomach had mucosa congestion and well defined tumor was noted. Photo 25 and 26 reveal stomach. Histology of mass was compatible with benign spindle cell tumor. It is demonstrated in photo (34).

There was a tumor at right frontal lobe of the brain measuring 3x2.5 cm (photo 28) and histology showed metastatic adenocarcinoma. It is illustrated in photo (33).

DISCUSSION

This patient had one month history of flaccid paraparesis, weight loss and appetite loss.

The etiology of flaccid paraparesis is usually benign; infection, vitamin deficiency, peripheral neuropathy. It is rarely related with malignancy- carcinomatous neuropathy (metastatic and paraneoplastic syndrome). This patient had low back pain; and, Xray lumbar spine showed features of spondylosis. Evidence of bony metastasis was not seen in lumbar spine Xray. He had chronic flaccid paraparesis without sensory involvement; and nerve conduction study revealed symmetrical length-dependent sensory-motor axonal polyneuropathy. CSF study was not done. He did not have diabetes mellitus or HIV infection; he was not alcoholic. Therefore, etiology of flaccid paraparesis in this patient was probably due to anti-TB induced peripheral neuropathy.

Peripheral neuropathy was reported as infrequent complication of isoniazid-based tuberculosis treatment. It is due to acquired pyridoxine deficiency with resultant axonal degeneration. If pyridoxine is prescribed with isoniazid from initiation of anti-TB therapy, peripheral neuropathy is unlikely. In fact, peripheral neuropathy is related with high dose of isoniazid and the longer duration of therapy (more than 6 months). The timing/onset of peripheral neuropathy varied; the earliest may be 2 weeks particularly in those with slow acetylator status. Risk factors for developing neuropathy after isoniazid therapy were reported as old age, slow acetylator status, diabetes, renal failure, alcoholism, malnutrition, HIV infection, chronic hepatic failure, pregnancy and certain genotype (Stettner et al., 2015) (Mafukidze et al., 2016). This patient was given vitamins and physiotherapy. Isoniazid can cause rapid onset of peripheral neuropathy with predominant motor symptoms and should be considered as a possible cause in cases presenting with such symptoms soon after starting the medication. The risk of neuropathy increases with the dose of isoniazid, and is not common when isoniazid is given at a standard 5 mg/kg dose. The body weight of this patient was 50 Kg; he took 300 mg of isoniazid daily. Symptoms after initiation of treatment in

patients receiving conventional doses rarely appear before 6 months (Mafukidze et al., 2016). This patient received 6 months course of anti-tubercular therapy 10 years ago; isoniazid, ethambutol, pyrazinamide and rifampicin. And paraparesis was a recent problem-one month prior to admission. Therefore, isoniazid induced peripheral neuropathy was unlikely.

Pyridoxine is preventative in low dosage and curative in high dosage in peripheral neuropathy induced by isoniazid (Steichen et al., 2006). Vitamin deficiency related peripheral neuropathy was less possible as vitamin supplements (thiamine, pyridoxine, cyanocobalamin) and physiotherapy did not improve motor power of lower limbs. There was no history of gastroenteritis or fever prior to weakness; thus, infective cause was unlikely in this patient.

At autopsy, adenocarcinoma lung was found; and metastasis to brain was seen. Therefore, flaccid paraparesis was due to malignancy related. Carcinomatous neuropathy or paraneoplastic syndromes was reported as non-metastatic manifestation of malignancy: small cell lung cancer (Kim et al., 2015), non-small cell lung cancer (Soomro et al., 2020), adenocarcinoma lung, carcinoma breast (Bahadoram et al., 2022), stomach and lymphoma.

The incidence of lung cancer has been increasing throughout the world. Paraneoplastic syndromes refer to clinical conditions that develop in relation to tumors, without physical effects of the primary or metastatic tumors. The development of paraneoplastic syndromes is not associated with the size of the primary tumor or the extent of metastases. It is usually seen in small-cell lung cancer as well as other types of lung cancer. The paraneoplastic syndromes developed in almost 1 in 10 patients with lung cancer; and it may be an indicator for the diagnosis of lung cancer. And, it can be seen during later stages of cancer or at the time of cancer recurrence (Tas, 2018). The identification of paraneoplastic syndromes can be helpful in the early diagnosis of occult cancers and timely treatment. Complete resolution of paraparesis after excision of the lung carcinoid paraneoplastic neurological syndrome was recorded by Furlan et al (Furlan et al., 2016). In this patient, paraparesis would have improved if we had resected lung cancer.

This patient had multi-system involvement clinically; paraparesis; depression; appetite loss; and weight loss. Common etiology in patient with multi-system involvement are disseminated infections like tuberculosis, connective tissue disorder like systemic lupus erythematosus, metabolic disorder like diabetes mellitus, sarcoidosis, malignancy like lymphoma and paraneoplastic syndromes. Autopsy revealed two major organ involvement; lungs and brain. And the histology proved that lung was primary (adenocarcinoma) and brain was secondary (metastasis). Therefore, this case highlighted the awareness of malignancy in patient with multi-system involvement.

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The patient was ex-smoker; there was no clubbing or cervical lymphadenopathy. Chest radiograph was compatible with old infective changes at both upper zones and left middle zone; prominent right hilar area was not obvious. The radiographic findings were consistent with old pulmonary tuberculosis; CT scan chest was not proceeded. Therefore, we missed carcinoma of right lung; autopsy findings revealed adenocarcinoma lung. It explained one month history of weight loss and appetite loss in this case. If we considered seriously on 'weight loss and appetite loss', we should have done CT scan chest. However, in low resource setting, doing advanced imaging like CT scan has some limitation. Moreover, the similarities between lung cancer and pulmonary TB was found in several reports (Keikha & Esfahani, 2018) (Luo et al., 2024). On the other hand, both diseases (histologically proved lung cancer and confirmed TB) were coexisting (Mahishi et al., 2024).

Having depression in this patient was secondary to paraparesis. Non-contrast CT scan head was normal. Contrast enhanced CT scan head was not done in this patient for 2 reasons: having normal non-contrast CT scan head and resource poor setting. He did not have features of raised intracranial pressure, pyramidal signs or papilledema. Autopsy revealed mass at right frontal lobe; histology was consistent with metastasis from adenocarcinoma lung. If we had done contrast enhanced CT scan head or MRI, frontal lobe metastasis would have detected earlier. And, the survival of this patient would have changed with new treatment (Y. Zhang et al., 2015).

Among histological types of lung cancer, squamous cell carcinoma still remains the commonest histological subtype followed by adenocarcinoma (Ganti et al., 2021). Non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) was found to have a high rate of brain metastasis (Wan et al., 2025) (Alfaraj et al., 2022) (Machaku et al., 2023) (Li et al., 2025). Chen et al suggested to perform mutation status of primary NSCLC because the differential distribution of brain metastases could be predicted from it (Chen et al., 2023). The future of management of lung cancer included advanced MRI techniques and specialised MRI methods to detect brain metastasis (Ghaderi et al., 2024). Moreover, brain biopsy was necessary to make a definitive diagnosis especially imaging findings were ambiguous (Huang et al., 2021) (Abana et al., 2020). Often the first line of imaging, contrast-enhanced CT was previously thought to be equivalent to MRI for the detection of metastases. MRI technology has been shown to be more sensitive than CT in detecting brain metastasis and is the preferred imaging of choice (X. Zhang et al., 2025). Therefore, we should have done MRI brain in this patient.

Spindle-cell tumors in the gastro-intestinal tract was reported as relatively uncommon tumours compared to epithelial tumours (Palazzo & Schulz, 1948) (Rasool et al., 2019) (Gama & Oliveira, 2024). Spindle cell tumors of gastro-

intestinal tract are non-epithelial in origin arising primarily from mesodermal tissue; the neurinoma or neurofibroma, the leiomyoma, and the fibroma. They are classified as "benign" and "malignant" spindle-cell tumor based on histology and roentgenologic criteria. In this patient, gastric subepithelial lesion was seen in gastroscopy which was done for hematemesis and melaena. And, it was found to be benign spindle cell tumor in histological examination. Therefore, it was a coincidental finding in this case.

In this patient, the primary site was right lung, adenocarcinoma; and frontal lobe lesion was secondary. It was reported that the majority of brain metastasis had multiple lesions (Alfaraj et al., 2022) (Machaku et al., 2023) (Li et al., 2025). In lung adenocarcinoma, frontal lobe and cerebellum were reported as common site of brain metastases (G. Wang et al., 2019) (Winslow et al., 2024). They preferentially involved the distal middle cerebral artery territory and cerebellum (Brain Metastases From Lung Adenocarcinoma May Preferentially Involve the Distal Middle Cerebral Artery Territory and Cerebellum, n.d.). Therefore, both primary site histology (adenocarcinoma lung) and the nature of brain metastasis (frontal lobe metastasis) supported previous reports.

Lung cancer usually presents with pulmonary symptoms such as cough, dyspnoea; and extrapulmonary symptoms with metastatic involvement of the brain may present as delirium or neurological deficits. However, some reports pointed out that presenting symptoms as bipolar disorder or depression may be the only initial manifestation of lung cancer with brain metastasis, (D'Souza & Srivastav, 2025) (Gama Marques, 2019). On the other hand, the location of brain metastases with known primary lung cancer is important because it had specific treatment (Y. Zhang et al., 2015) and independent prognostic value (Noh & Walbert, 2018) (Cacho-Díaz et al., 2019) (Takei et al., 2016).

CONCLUSION

In patient with flaccid paraparesis, paraneoplastic syndrome should be considered as one of the possible causes. Brain metastasis may manifest as depression or bipolar mood disorder. Frontal lobe metastasis from adenocarcinoma lung is not uncommon. In patient with pulmonary TB, common in developing countries, both clinical and chest radiographic findings may not be clearly differentiated from lung cancer. In resource poor setting, it is not easy to perform molecular marker, genotyping and some imaging; and definite diagnosis may be missed.

Therefore, clinician should have awareness of lung cancer in patient with pulmonary tuberculosis. Benign spindle cell tumor of stomach is a rare finding.

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Photo (1) Chest radiograph taken in February 2025 showing patchy opacities in both upper zones with hilar enlargement

Photo (2) Chest radiograph taken in March 2025 showing patchy opacities in both upper zones more on right side right lung

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Photo (3) Lateral view of thoraco-lumbar spine X ray showing features of spondylosis

Photo (4) AP view of thoraco-lumbar spine X ray appears normal

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Photo (5) NECT Head cross sectional view

Photo (6) NECT Head cross sectional view

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Photo (7) NECT Head cross sectional view

Photo (8) NECT Head coronal sectional view

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Photo (9) NECT Head cross sectional view

Photo (10) NECT Head lateral view

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Photo (11) NECT Head lateral view

Photo (12) NECT Head lateral view

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Photo (13) NECT Head lateral view

Photo (14) Subepithelial lesion in body of stomach in Gastroscopy (close up view)

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Photo (15) Features of gastritis and gastric subepithelial lesion in Gastroscopy

Photo (16) Features of gastritis in Gastroscopy

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Photo (17) Features of gastritis in Gastroscopy

Photo (18) Features of severe pangastritis with red spot in Gastroscopy

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Photo (19) Features of atrophic changes in Gastroscopy (pale, thin stomach lining and increased visibility of the vasculature due to reduced mucosal thickness)

Photo (20) Features of atrophic gastritis in Gastroscopy

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Photo (21) Autopsy of right thoracic cavity containing serious pleural effusion about 1,200 cc

Photo (22) Autopsy of left thoracic cavity containing serious pleural effusion (100 cc) and pleural adhesion

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Photo (23.a) Autopsy of left lung showing area of consolidation

Photo (23.b) Autopsy of left lung showing area of consolidation

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Photo (24) Autopsy of right lung showing mass in right hilum

Photo (25.a) Autopsy of mucosa of stomach showing mild gastric erosion and mass

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Photo (25.b) Autopsy of stomach (serosal surface)

Photo (26) Autopsy of mucosa of stomach showing mild gastric erosion and mass (Spindle cell tumor of stomach)

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Photo (27.a) Autopsy of heart revealing normal coronary arteries (no stent thrombosis at LAD and normal right coronary artery)

Photo (27.b) Autopsy of heart revealing normal coronary arteries (no stent thrombosis at LAD and normal right coronary artery)

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Photo (28.a) Autopsy of brain showing tumor at Right frontal lobe; histology was metastatic adenocarcinoma

Photo (28.b) Autopsy of cut section of brain showing tumor at Right frontal lobe; histology was metastatic adenocarcinoma

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Photo (29.a) Autopsy of spleen (external surface)

Photo (29.b) Autopsy of cut section of spleen revealing soft and septic

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Photo (30) Autopsy of liver showing congestion

Photo (31) Autopsy of kidneys having normal appearance

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Photo (32.a) Histology from growth at right lung revealing sheets of Acinar (gland-forming) malignant cells in alveolar space compatible with adenocarcinoma lung (X10)

Photo (32.b) Histology from growth at right lung revealing sheets of Acinar (gland-forming) malignant cells in alveolar space (X 40)

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Photo (33.a) Histology from tumor at right frontal lobe showing metastasis (metastatic adenocarcinoma) (X10)

Photo (33.b) Histology from tumor at right frontal lobe showing metastasis (metastatic adenocarcinoma) (X40)

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Photo (34.a) Histology from subepithelial lesion of stomach showing elongated, fusiform cells resembling fibroblasts. They have uniform nuclei, low mitotic activity, and no necrosis compatible with benign spindle cell tumor (X 10)

Photo (34.b) Histology from subepithelial lesion of stomach showing elongated, fusiform cells resembling fibroblasts. They have uniform nuclei, low mitotic activity, and no necrosis compatible with benign spindle cell tumor (X40)